

Sampling and estimation (left)

h) Assess power of models and data by comparing $\hat{\rho}_{i,ms,age}$ to $\rho_{R,age}$

g) Estimate parameters from $\mathbf{M}_{i,ms,age}$, including $\hat{\rho}_{i,ms,age}$

f) Sample from $CH_{observed}$ to get 50 realized datasets (i) for each monitoring scenario ($\mathbf{M}_{i,ms,age}$)

e) Define 4 monitoring scenarios (ms) varying by annual cohort size

Simulation process (right)

a) Empirical analysis of real data

b) Simulate S_{age} and f_{age} based on empirical results and hypothesis additive harvest ($\rho_{simulated1,age}$)

c) Simulate population with known-fate and observed capture histories (CH_{known} , $CH_{observed}$)

d) Calculate vital rates of simulated population from CH_{known} ($\rho_{R,age}$)